

Social Support in Hypertension Treatment Adherence: A Qualitative Study in Ghana

Thesis for the completion of a masters program at the University of Ghana, West Africa

Rose Therra Nortey MPhil, BSc, RGN

Advisors: Hyunkyoungh Oh PhD, MSN, RN; Gwendolyn Patience Mensah PhD, MPhil, BA, RM, SRN, FGCNM; Gladys Dzansi PhD, MPhil, BA, SRN;

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This research was solely funded by the researcher and there are no conflicts of interest.

Ethical Consideration

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Social Media

Hypertension is easy to diagnose but often remains undetected; simple to treat but often remains untreated; despite the availability of medicines, treatment is not adequately effective, however social support is the new trend to management.

Abstract

Background: Hypertension is a leading global public health concern, contributing to 55.6% of annual mortality and affecting nearly one billion individuals worldwide.

Objective: The aim of the study is to explore the experiences of social support in treatment adherence of persons living with hypertension.

Method: This study utilized a qualitative research design ensuring methodological rigor and credibility. Semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions were conducted, audio recorded transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic content analysis.

Results: Participants primarily relied on companionship and emotional social support to maintain treatment adherence. While immediate blood pressure optimization was not achieved, improvements in overall health and well-being were observed.

Conclusion: This study highlights social support as crucial factor in hypertension treatment adherence. Participants demonstrated how various social support types-informational, companionship, emotional, and tangible positively influenced their adherence behaviors, reinforcing the need for integrated support strategies in hypertension management.

Keywords: social support; Hypertension; treatment / medication adherence; qualitative.

Background

Hypertension (HTN) remains the world's leading public health problem, with 55.6% mortality annually and affecting nearly one billion people around the globe. It is estimated to rise to about 1.56 billion adults worldwide by end of 2025, with two-thirds in Low-Middle-Income Countries.¹ Hypertension is classified as a blood pressure reading of $\geq 130 / 80$ mm Hg or requiring antihypertensive medication.¹⁴ Adherence to medication, exercise or physical activeness, well-balanced diet with high fiber, low cholesterol foods, low salt intake, reduced alcohol consumption, avoiding smoking, maintaining healthy body weight and regular blood pressure checks has shown to reduce the risk of stroke and coronary heart disease significantly.^{3,5,14}

Annual global rates of nonadherence range from 50% to 80% yearly with higher rates in chronic diseases especially in HTN due to its silence nature.⁵ Treatment adherence is reported to be worse in Low-Middle-Income Countries, including Ghana, due to poor accessibility of effective antihypertensive medicines and healthcare facilities.⁴ The effect of antihypertensive medication relies greatly on social support for better outcomes.⁸⁻¹⁰ Social support is an essential facilitator of better outcomes in HTN management, and outweighs the effect of poor prognosis and reduces disability adjusted life years in patients.^{6,7}

In Ghana, many researchers focus on identifying determinants of treatment nonadherence, but investigation on social support in treatment adherence is limited.^{5,7,12,3} A Study conducted in Ethiopia recommended that family support would be the best way to help persons living with HTN to adhere to treatment in order to have optimal health.¹³ Other reviewed articles recommended social support as an effective tool in optimizing treatment adherence and effective blood pressure control to curb disability and mortality.^{34,25,6,26,28,29,24} Research has also

shown that patients get more comfortable and easily comply with treatment when it comes to their familiar persons.¹⁶

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages, focusing on reducing global mortality rates and addressing health issues.¹⁴ In the context of HTN, strong social support networks can significantly enhance treatment adherence, as individuals are more likely to manage their condition effectively when backed by family, friends, and community resources thus reducing the devastating complications and mortality in HTN management.²

The study aims to examine the types of social support, its impact on HTN treatment adherence, and barriers faced by patients at the Outpatient Department (OPD) of the two Metroclinics at La-Nkwantanang Municipality in Ghana.

Methods

Research Design

This qualitative study was conducted based on Lehmann's medication adherence model (Fig. 1). The medication adherence model by Lehmann et al²³ was the most fitting for this study because the model aligns with the researcher's conceptual framework, detailing the key constructs relevant to treatment adherence in HTN²³: disease, demographic and socio-economic factors (social support); patient and close relatives; health care system and medication.

Lehmann's model emphasizes the critical role of social support in treatment adherence, and it is crucial for improving patient outcomes. In view of this, the study employed an exploratory descriptive qualitative design to understand the experiences of social support in treatment adherence in persons living with HTN.²³

Semi-structured interviews using open-ended questions were purposely applied to bring out personal views of the participants attending the two Metroclinics in the La-Nkwantanang Municipality.

Qualitative research design is essential for understanding participant behavior for unassuming observation and description of complex phenomena, enabling participants to freely articulate their perspectives through telephone interviews.^{20,18,22} According to Creswell,¹⁹ humans have varied expressions to situations, due to this, exploratory descriptive qualitative design was chosen to delve into experiences of social support in treatment adherence to persons living with HTN.

Interviewer Qualifications

The PI possesses a robust foundation in qualitative methodologies bolstered by comprehensive training in qualitative research design. This training has equipped the PI with the necessary theoretical and practical skills to approach qualitative studies systematically and effectively. The study was in fulfillment of an MPhil Nursing program, driven by a profound passion for addressing the issue of nonadherence to HTN management among regular clients. Through academic research and practical experiences in clinical settings, the PI gained insights into the significant challenges faced by patients in following prescribed treatment regimens. This commitment to understanding and resolving adherence challenges in HTN management reflects a strong foundation in both theoretical and applied nursing practices, equipping the PI with the qualifications and readiness to undertake this investigation.

Sample Population and Setting

According to Creswell and Creswell,²² saturation is achieved when no new themes emerge from participant responses. In the context of HTN, treatment adherence and social

support, saturation was confirmed after 12 interviews, as recurring patterns in patient experiences and support structures emerged consistently. Purposive sampling techniques were employed to select eligible participants from the two Metroclinics, ensuring a focused approach to gather relevant insights. Eligibility extended beyond age, diagnosis and medications as participants were chosen to have diversity in socioeconomic status and disease inform variety of perspectives. Participants aged 18 and 65 diagnosed with HTN and are on antihypertensive treatment (AHT) were selected based on their willingness to share their experiences on social support in HTN management.

Data Collection Procedure

The participants were selected using purposive convenience sampling methods through the outpatient HTN clinic at the two Metroclinics. Research aims and objectives, and consent forms were also explained. The telephone interviews were scheduled for a maximum of an hour per participant. Participants provided permission for data recording and were informed that data collection was for research purposes and would be anonymized. They were also told of their right to be part or withdraw at any time without any coercion.

A semi-structured interview guide (Table 2) was used to conduct interviews via telephone, facilitating accessibility while maintaining safety COVID-19 protocols. Telephone interviews were chosen for participants' convenience and scheduling constraints. Also, to encourage openness about personal health matters. Interested, eligible participants who provided consent were included in the study. The interviews were audio recorded with participants' permission and field notes were kept during the interviews. The data collected were transcribed verbatim to preserve participant responses.

Ethical Committee Approval

Ethical approval was sought from Ghana Health Service with an introductory letter from the School of Nursing and Midwifery, University of Ghana. The approved letter was sent to the Health Directorate of La-Nkwantanang Municipal where it was endorsed for the appropriate research setting.

Data analysis

The PI conducted iterative coding through repeated transcript reviews and thematic analysis. Audio were replayed multiple times to capture the meanings, ensure alignment and themes. Thematic analysis was structured based on Lincoln and Guba's framework which ensures methodological rigor. Data was collated, then analyzed in the reflection of the model and research objectives. Methodological rigor in qualitative research is essential for ensuring the trustworthiness of collected data which reflects the credibility and reality of participants' experiences. Credibility was achieved by establishing rapport and building trust with participants while employing member-checking and peer debriefing to further ensure that findings accurately reflect participants lived experiences and reduce researcher bias.²⁰ Transferability was enhanced through rich, thick descriptions of participants' experiences and detailed contextual documentation, allowing future researchers to apply findings to similar settings. An audit trail was maintained, consisting of all transcribed data and field notes, which provides transparency and aids in monitoring the researcher's decisions throughout the study.^{19,21}

Dependability was thorough by description of data collection processes, including the timeline and participant details, reinforcing the rigor of the study. Confirmability was ensured by articulating the researcher's assumptions and maintaining an audit trail that documents the

research journey. Finally, the study participants confirmed that their views are accurately represented, their interests are honored, reinforcing the overall trustworthiness of the study.¹⁹⁻²²

Lehmann’s medication adherence model describes five main constructs influencing HTN management: disease-related knowledge; demographic and socio-economic factors such as educational and financial resources; patient and close relatives social support types; health care system: access to care and care facility organization; and medication factors including regimen and effects in persons living with HTN.²³

Figure 1

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Saturation was reached after interviewing 12 participants comprising of five males and seven females between ages 25 years and 64. Among the 12, were six married; four were singles; one was widowed and one divorcee. Ten were Christians and two were Muslims. All were employed. All were Ghanaians. All participants had education of some sort and could speak good English. Table 1 shows participants' demographics.

Main Findings:

There were four main themes and 15 subthemes (Table 3) that emerged from the interviews as guided by the Medication adherence model.²³

Theme 1: Effects of Symptoms and Severity of HTN

The effects of symptoms and severity in HTN emerged as a crucial theme, influencing participants HTN management through five interconnecting subthemes:

1.1 Patient-Care Provider Relationship. Trust between patients and providers impacted adherence. Participants expressed that positive patient-provider interactions improved adherence to treatment recommendations:

“... a lot of headaches... a Nurse advised me not to stop ... she encouraged me... I always take it.” (male participant)

“I was also advised to be serious with my medicines so I wouldn't suffer any preventable consequences”. (female participant)

1.2 Patient's Disease Experiences. Participants who were unaware of their HTN status described their adherence journeys after diagnosis:

“...but until then I didn't know I had HTN”. (female participant)

“... I was reading around 170/100mmHg but gradually, now about 140/90mmHg” (female participant)

1.3 Patient's Attitude toward Disease and Medicine. Most participants had improved their attitude towards recommended guidelines and developed their own strategies towards adherence.

... “Always take my medicines since I was put on them. I take them first thing in the morning”. (male participant)

“At times I get headaches and restlessness, but this could be due to work stress...” (female participant)

1.4 Medicine Effects. The different effects of medicines on participants are weighed positively to know how efficacious the medicines are in the treatment of HTN.

“At the beginning, the medicines gave me a lot of uneasiness and dizziness...I complained to Dr, he advised I take them at night”. (male participant)

1.5 Self-Care management. This reveals how the patients adjust and adapt to recommendations of health care professionals in caring for themselves with the treatment of HTN.

“Mostly followed recommendations. I try jogging on Saturdays and Sundays...”
(male participant).

Most participants improved their health and wellness through recommended strategies from their health professionals.

Theme 2: Types of Experiences of social support

Participants described their various forms of social support received from family, friends, religious groups and their community, and highlighting the role of adherence to HTN treatment. The social support types are informational, companionship, tangible, and emotional social support.

2.1 Informational Social Support. This played a crucial role in participants’ understanding of their diagnosis and treatment. This enabled them to have informed decisions in adherence to their HTN regimen:

“... It was at this point that the Dr told me that I have HTN...” (male participant)

“...they said my BP was very high...180/100mmHg... was given medicines...”

(female participant)

2.2 Companionship Support. This encouraged treatment and accountability as family members ensured adherence and maximized health:

“...the children are supportive. They encouraged me to take my medicines...”

(female participant).

“I told my wife, and she accepted it and is making sure I follow what the Dr says...” (male participant).

“...Also, my family encourage me to take care of myself and keep taking my medicines so I could become better...” (male participant)

2.3 Tangible Support. This is the tangible support, particularly financial assistance, which plays a key role in accessibility to medicines. Participants referenced the National Health Insurance Scheme and community-based funds, assisting financial burdens and supporting adherence:

“The National Health Insurance Scheme mostly covers the medicines and bills...”

(male participant)

“My church and pastors sometimes help from the widowhood fund...” (female participant)

“I have Muslim friends both Drs and Nurses I consult when am in doubt...” (male participant)

2.4 Emotional Support. Limited emotional support affected participants HTN treatment adherence:

“Mostly, am pressed with time so I normally meet the Dr who cared for me ...”

(male participant)

Overall, participants verbalized the effectiveness of social support types for a better life and wellness.

Theme 3: Barriers to Social Support. This explores the barriers that hinder effective social support in HTN treatment adherence. Common challenges that emerged were disruptions in interpersonal relationships, healthcare system inefficiencies and financial limitations which affected treatment adherence:

“... health professionals are ... many times they are not patient.” (male participant)

“At times too, the queue is long, and we delay...”. (female participant)

“...For my medicines, it (NHIS) doesn't cover the cost anymore especially the Nifedipine”. (male participant)

“There is a lot of miscommunications about HTN...” (female participant)

Overall, the experiences barriers to social support were minimal among four participants. This denotes that the majority were more encouraged in this study.

3.1 Care Provider Attitude. Care provider attitude impacted participants adherence experiences. Many expressed frustrations at providers communication styles:

“...they should tone down on ... but many times they are not patient.” (male participant)

3.2 Patient's Experiences. Participants experience in relation to support persons:

“Most often am discouraged by my husband ... I wish there's a way to stop taking the medicines.” (female participant)

3.3 Care Organization. Participants experienced long waiting times and appointments delays made adherence challenging:

“At times too, the queue is long, and we delay, ... to go to work or attend to other things”. (female participant)

Participants reported that work and religious commitments do affect adherence:

“... due to church activities and work stresses, I forget the medicines...” (male participant)

“There hasn't been any help or support from both in the community or church...”
(female participant)

3.4 Care Access. Access to limited healthcare resources like counselling and financial aid played an important role in adherence:

“...no specific counselling or education”. (female participant)

“It worried me ... I know that HTN is not cured and stays with one for a long time or for life.” (male participant). The support persons discouraged treatment recommendations which could be tantamount to HTN complications.

Theme 4: Barriers to Medication Adherence. This theme explores the challenges that hinder consistent medication adherence among participants. Barriers expressed by participants include forgetfulness, discouragement, treatment expectations, and side effects which affected their adherence to HTN management.

4.1 Medication Barriers. Participants reported struggling with medication adherence due to life pressures, misinformation, and emotional discouragement:

“At times, due to church activities and work stresses, I forget the medicines ...BP has gone up when I went for check-up”. (male participant)

“Normally, I ask about the BP reading. So, it is through this that they may tell me is low or high”. (female participant)

“Most often am discouraged by my...I wish there’s a way to help me stop taking the medicines.” (female participant)

“...Because am expecting the medicines to help with HTN but mostly the BP goes down and comes up at times. (female participant)

“Sometimes I feel tired or discouraged to take the medicines...”. (male participant)

“I learnt it (medicines) can cause fibroids...it weakens the heart and that you may even get stroke”. (female participant)

4.2 Treatment Complexity. These shaped participants’ adherence including stress-induced BP fluctuations, and alternative medicine suggestions:

“... I get discouraged because I don’t get expected BP readings”. (female participant)

“...but was stressed ... I think is the stress that triggered the situation; however, I was hoping that the BP will return to normal after everything but still...” (male participant)

“In the beginning, I used to get palpitations and uneasiness when I take the medicines”. (male participant)

“They encouraged that I do local herbs like adding more garlic into food...”
(male participant)

Participants remained hopeful about achieving better health outcomes despite facing adherence barriers such as medication side effects, poor patient education, fluctuation in BP readings, and external discouragement from support systems.

Discussion

The study objectives aimed to explore the effects of social support in treatment adherence to HTN using the Lehmann model of adherence. The findings of the study were compared with previous studies for strengths, weaknesses, and uniqueness.

Theme 1. Effects of Symptoms and Severity of HTN

The study explored the role of social support in HTN treatment adherence using Lehmann model of medication adherence. Findings were analyzed in relation to previous studies, identifying strengths, limitations and unique contributions to the field.

1.1 Patient-Care Provider Relationship

The patient-care provider relationship plays an important role in HTN treatment adherence, fostering trust and improving patient cooperation. Findings aligned with a study conducted in China, where participants education was emphasized as an effective adherence strategy.²⁴ Despite extensive counseling on lifestyle modifications, participants verbalized that healthcare providers did not actively involve social support persons in treatment modules. This gap aligns with previous studies in Ghana, where family and community support have been underutilized despite proven roles in adherence in HTN management.^{7,11,3,28} Incorporating social support systems in treatment plans enhances long-term commitment to HTN treatment. Similarly, a study in Eritrea highlighted the importance of counselling on lifestyle modifications for optimal HTN management.²⁵ Also, participants were assigned to HTN clinic for effective follow-up, care and counseling which is unique to this study. This differs from the study conducted in Iran on OPD patients with HTN where there was no follow-up clinic, care or counselling.²⁶

While immediate AHT was initiated 11 out of 12 participants, only one case did serial BP checks. This contrasts a study conducted in Ghana in 2010, emphasized that serial BP checks over several weeks provide a more reliable diagnosis, limiting inaccuracies caused by stressors, physical activity, or underlying condition.¹²

Furthermore, healthcare providers encouraged participants to adhere to avoiding smoking, reducing alcohol consumption, physical exercise, lowering fats and oils, eating more fruit and vegetables, and taking prescribed medications. This study revealed that all participants made efforts to adhere as in the study by Ofori-Asenso et al.²² In this study, none of the participants mentioned maintenance of healthy body weight as a prerequisite for optimal HTN management.

1.2 Patient's Disease Experiences

Hypertension is known to be a silent disease as many go undiagnosed until complications arise.^{1,26} This parallels with global observations, emphasizing the need for pre-emptive screening and early detection.^{14,2} Findings in this study supports previous research in Ghana which advocates for walk-in BP screening services in healthcare facilities to improve early HTN detection.^{26,16} Implementing these for diseases like HTN, diabetes and cancer could enhance preventive healthcare.

Participants demonstrated misconceptions about the long-term management of HTN despite counseling on HTN. Many expressed their frustration at the unsettled BP readings, believing that short-term optimization would indicate treatment success.^{13,31,30}

These were in sync with studies conducted in Iran, Ethiopia, and Nigeria. Where inadequate patient education led to unrealistic treatment expectations.^{4,7,26,16}

Social support emerged as an effective tool in treatment adherence to HTN reinforcing previous studies that highlights its effectiveness.^{13,31,30} Participants who received consistent encouragement from family and community networks had greater commitment to long-term treatment adherence.

1.3 Patient's Attitude toward Disease and Medicine

In this study, some participants resisted the HTN treatment due to their spiritual beliefs, aligning with findings in Ghana.^{4,8,11,12,28} Also, in this study some participants also experienced worsening symptoms, including muscle weakness, palpitations, dizziness and headaches as they disregarded their treatment. This is parallel to some studies in Ghana that reinforces the need for early adherence and consistency.^{11,12}

Adherence rates 80% which is notably higher than in studies in India (75%), Ethiopia, Iran and Nigeria.^{13, 26,30,32} These variations may be due to differences in healthcare accessibility, cultural perceptions of illness, and patient education strategies.

In contrast to some previous study findings in Ghana,^{33,34,6} two participants refused recommendations of alternative medicines along the prescribed AHT. This implies that participants had stronger healthcare guidance in their treatment.

Again, several participants reported side effects from prescribed medicines prompting health professionals to adjust dosing schedules or recommend alternative medications the contrast this contrast with studies in Malaysia, Iran, Korea, and China^{35-36,26,24} where participants did not report significant medication-related concerns. Such differences may reflect variations in pharmacological formulations, patient tolerance levels, or healthcare monitoring practices.²⁷ Furthermore, encouragement from family and friends played a role in sustaining treatment adherence reinforcing insights from prior research.³⁷⁻³⁹

Future interventions should strengthen patient-provider relationships and integrate structured social support mechanisms to optimize long term HTN management.

1.4 Medicine Effects

Medication effects vary among individuals influencing adherence. While some patients tolerate treatment well others experienced side effects requiring adjustment to optimize efficacy.^{4,36}

In this study findings indicated that eight participants experienced no issues with medication from the start, whereas two participants encountered unpleasant side effects. Consequently, health providers modified the treatment regimen for those two individuals based on results from lab investigations. This outcome is consistent with research conducted previously in Ghana where participants were assessed using various AHT to identify the most effective options.^{34,11,12} Echoing earlier research from Ghana, this study also emphasized the significance of personalized treatment assessments to optimize AHT,^{34,11,27} the findings highlight the critical need for ongoing monitoring and necessary adjustments in HTN management to promote adherence

Theme 2. Effects of Social Support

This study examined the role of social support in HTN treatment adherence, it's direct effect on patient commitments and the influence of social support in sustaining long-term adherence.

2.1 Informational Social Support

Informational social support encompasses essential health related knowledge including guidance from healthcare professionals, referrals for specialized care, individualized treatment recommendations.³⁹

Participants in this study received HTN diagnosis following comprehensive health assessments and clinical lab investigations consistent with findings from Ethiopia and Nigeria.^{13,17} However Kizzie Hayford's study in Ghana suggests that precise HTN diagnosis requires multiple BP readings overtime,¹² emphasizing the need of extended monitoring. Participants in this study received encouragement from family and close relatives to adhere to treatment aligning with research by Affusim et al, Lamptey et al, and Maslakpak et al.^{31,29,5} These studies indicate that strong family networks contribute to improve BP control and adherence, particularly in African settings where communal support plays vital role in health management.

Razatul's study in Malaysia contradicts these findings showing that despite strong family and social support networks participants were discouraged from adhering to treatments³⁶ this suggests that while social support can be beneficial cultural attributes toward HTN and medication acceptance may influence whether such support leads to positive adherence outcomes.

2.2 Tangible Social Support

Tangible social support encompasses financial assistance, physical aid, essential services and material resources that help individuals manage their healthcare needs. In Ghana, external family systems ensure that an individual's illness is collective concern, reinforcing strong social support structures.^{39,37,17} This study found that participants received unwavering assistance from family and friends, reducing financial burdens associated with HTN management.

Findings align with Eritrean healthcare policies where the government ensures free HTN treatments for all citizens.²⁵ However, contrasting studies in Ghana suggests

NHIS inefficiencies hinder accessibility to HTN care.^{33,29,3} Despite these concerns participants in this study reported effective NHIS coverage for commonly prescribed AHT. Most participants in this study were financially stable and able to afford their medications reflecting employment security as a determinant of healthcare accessibility. However, two individuals occasionally relied on family support for treatment costs emphasizing the role of social networks in addressing financial barriers.

2.3 Companionship Social Support

Companionship social support fosters a sense of belonging and is primarily provided by family, close relatives and community members. It encompasses emotional acceptance, affection and intimacy contributing to overall well-being.³⁹

This study found that married participants with strong spousal support achieved optimal BP control and better adherence to HTN treatment. These findings align with studies in Nigeria which suggest that marriage contributes to improve physical health, reduce stress and enhanced treatment adherence.^{31,1,30} This study observed no adherence disparities among singles, widowed and divorced participants contrasting findings from research conducted in Ethiopia and Nigeria^{13,40} which reported low adherence rates in these demographic groups. This divergence may be attributed to variations in access to support networks, personal motivation, or healthcare guidance.

Family close relatives played a crucial role in reinforcing treatment adherence, mirroring findings from Affusim et al, Magrin et al, and Maslampak et al.^{31,15,5} This suggests that strong companionship support facilitates optimize BP control and maximized adherence, further highlighting the importance of integrated family-based interventions in HTN management.

2.4 Emotional Social Support

Emotional social support encompasses expressions of affection, care and encouragement, which plays a crucial role in helping individuals cope with illness and sustain treatment adherence.⁴¹ Most participants received emotional support primarily from family and friends who provided reassurance and encouragement, helping them focus on their health rather than the burden of their HTN diagnosis. Findings from this study aligning with previous research highlighting the importance of emotional support in treatment adherence.³⁸ Maslajak et al,⁵ and Monteiro and Hariharan³⁸ found that patients who received emotional reinforcement from close networks were more likely to maintain consistent HTN treatment. While participants in this study received continuous emotional encouragement, those in and Naghavi et al's²⁶ research experienced less sustained support, contributing to reduced adherence rates. This suggests that consistent emotional reinforcement may be crucial in preventing treatment fatigue and dropout.

Theme 3. Barriers to Social Support

This study identifies barriers to social support primarily within healthcare settings, focusing on limitations in provider interactions, patients' experiences, facility organization and accessibility.

These challenges hinder effective HTN management and adherence.

3.1 Care Provider Attitude

Four out of 12 participants reported improper diagnostic communication, incorrect prescriptions due to poor follow-up, feelings of intimidation, and inadequate medications supply. Similar concerns were documented in studies from Ghana, Malaysia, India and

Nigeria where participants received diagnosis without sufficient emotional support from healthcare providers.^{31,34,25,36}

Also, challenges in electronic health record systems have led to discrepancies in patient history documentation. Consequently, prescribers unfamiliar with previous treatments may issue inconsistent medication regimens causing patient confusion and potential nonadherence.³⁶ Irregular NHIS payments to government facilities have contributed to inconsistencies in medication supply and healthcare service delivery as a result detention patient frequently face incomplete prescriptions, exacerbating treatment nonadherence rates.^{31,34,25,36}

3.2 Patient Experiences

This study revealed significant gaps in patient education regarding HTN treatment including misconceptions about disease effects, treatment duration and the medication impact. Many participants were informed about HTN but lacked clear understanding of its long-term management. These findings aligned with previous studies in Ghana and Malaysia where patients exhibited similar misunderstandings about HTN chronic nature and required lifelong treatment adherence.^{7,36}

3.3 Care Organization

In this study, participants identified several healthcare facility challenges including prolonged wait times, insufficient specialist reviews, overcrowded waiting areas and inconsistencies in NHIS medication supplies. Similarly, challenges have been reported in studies conducted in parts of Ghana, Malaysia and Ethiopia where patients frequently experienced extended wait times, limited consultations with healthcare professionals and inadequate specialist to review.^{13,3,36} Also, participants noted irregularities in NHIS

medication distribution, a finding a code in prior studies. Supply inconsistencies limit access to prescribed AHT, increasing the likelihood of nonadherence in treatment discontinuation.^{30,33,8}

3.4 Care Access

Participants reported consistent access to some routine medications and clinical services; however, essential diagnostic tests such as ultrasound scans and electrocardiography were unavailable within the facilities study, forcing them to seek costly external services. this aligns with findings from Eritrea, where similar healthcare accessibility issues were noted.²⁵

Theme 4. Barriers to Medication Adherence

This theme examines the challenges that hinder consistent adherence to prescribed medications. Factors such as forgetfulness, inadequate community support, in treatment complexity emerged as key barriers impacting long-term HTN management.

4.1 Medication Barriers

Forgetfulness was the most common barrier to adherence, followed by insufficient community support, limited patient education on HTN and AHT, and difficulties with maintaining long-term treatment regimens these findings align with research conducted in India, which identified similar adherence challenges among HTN patients.¹⁰

4.2 Treatment Complexity

Treatment complexity encompasses multiple adherence challenges, including medication regimens, required lifestyle modifications, and physiological adaptations to long-term treatment. Participants in this study reported forgetfulness and treatment duration as primary hurdles, mirroring findings from studies conducted in Ghana previously.^{33 9 11 12 3}

This looks at the totality of patients' treatment modules. Treatment complexity includes the challenges faced in relation to medicines, lifestyle modifications, adaptation to treatment and adherence. In this study, the participants' main challenge to medicines was forgetfulness and length of treatment. This is in matching to some studies done in Ghana.^{33,10,9,27}

Limitations of the Study

The study was limited by small sample size, necessitating further research to enhance generalizability. Again, this study was conducted in a single municipality in Ghana which limits the generalizability of findings. Future research should include multiple regions to assess variations in social support mechanisms across diverse healthcare settings. Also, this study exclusively focused on outpatients of HTN, limiting insights into inpatient experiences induce with comorbid conditions. Future research should incorporate a broader patient population to provide a more comprehensive perspective on adherence challenges.

Conclusion

This study explored the impact of social support on treatment adherence among patients with HTN, providing valuable insight into patient experiences, healthcare system barriers, and medication adherence challenges. Findings indicate that strong social support networks, including family, friends, and healthcare professionals, play a critical role in enforcing adherence behaviors, ensuring treatment continuity, and optimizing BP control. Despite these positive influences, several barriers to adherence were identified, including healthcare system inefficiencies, long wait times, inconsistent medication supply, and inadequate patient education regarding HTN's long-term management. Additionally, misconceptions about medication

regimens and treatment duration contribute to frustration, impacting patient engagement. The study underscores patients and engagements.

The study underscores the need for improved patient education, streamlined healthcare services, and enhanced access to specialized care to foster better adherence outcomes. Given the small sample size and geographical limitations, countrywide research should explore adherence behaviors across broader populations and settings to deepen understanding and refine intervention strategies. By integrating social support systems into HTN management, healthcare providers can create more comprehensive adherence frameworks, ultimately reducing complications, improving patient well-being, and enhancing long-term treatment effectiveness.

Clinical Resources

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What's New

- The study proved that social support is an effective tool to medication adherence in adults living with Hypertension.
- The explored social support types played different roles in the lives of the participants and helped with blood pressure optimization.

Fig 1: Medication Adherence Model for Chronic Patients (Lehmann et al., 2014)

Table 1

Participants information	Gender	Age	Occupation	Marital Status	Religion	Ethnicity	Educational level
Participant ID							
Okukuseku	Male	42	Engineer	Married	Christian	Dagomba	Tertiary
Kaka	Female	54	Business woman	Divorcee	Christian	Akan	Tertiary
Kako	Female	64	Business woman	Widow	Christian	Akan	Secondary
Okeley	Female	52	Trader	Married	Christian	Ahanta	Junior High
Krakue	Male	48	Teacher	Married	Christian	Ewe	Tertiary
Okun	Female	35	Health assistant	Single	Muslim	Mosi	Tertiary
Oko	Male	56	Businessman	Married	Muslim	Dagomba	Tertiary
Kaks	Male	32	Civil Engineer	Single	Christian	Akan	Tertiary
Krakyee	Female	39	Caterer	Married	Christian	Akan	Tertiary
Okuranu	Male	49	Banker	Married	Christian	Akan	Tertiary
Okraa	Female	25	Fashion Designer	Single	Christian	Akan	Secondary
Kakroo	Female	40	Administrator	Single	Christian	Sefwi	Tertiary

Table 2: Interview questions

Area	Questions
Hypertension	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. When were you diagnosed with Hypertension?2. What do you know about Hypertension?3. How did you take the news of your diagnosis?4. In your view, do you think there are factors that help or deteriorate your Hypertension situation?5. Do you stop taking your medicines when better or worse and why?
Adherence	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What types of medicines to do take and how many?2. How long have you been on your medicines?3. What do you think about your medicines?4. What other recommendations are you working with as treatment for Hypertension?
Social Support	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Who can really count to be dependable on when you need help?2. Whom can you really count on to help you to feel more relaxed when under pressure or tensed?3. Who accepts you totally both at your best and worst points?4. Whom can you really count on to care about you regardless of what is happening to you?5. Whom can you really count to help you feel better when you are feeling generally down-in-the-dumps?

Table 3: Themes and Subthemes – revise this table. What does ‘data’ mean in this table?

Themes	Subthemes
Effects of symptoms and severity of HTN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patient-Care Provider Relationship ● Patient’s Disease Experiences ● Patient’s Attitude toward Disease and Medicine ● Medicine Effects ● Self-Care management
Effects of social support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informational social support ● Tangible social support ● Companionship social support ● Emotional social support
Barriers to Social Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Care Provider Attitude ● Patient’s Experiences ● Care Organization ● Care Access

Abbreviations

AHT- Antihypertensive treatment

HTN- Hypertension

NHIS- National Health Insurance Scheme

WHO- World Health Organization